

Effect of some 2-Arylhydrazonobenzothiazoles on the Kinetics of Corrosion of Al—Mn Alloy in Acidic Medium

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The effect of 2-(*o*-OH, *p*-OH, *p*-OCH₃ and *p*-N(CH₃)₂ benzaldehyde) hydrazonobenzothiazoles on the kinetics of corrosion of Al—Mn alloy in 2.5 mol dm⁻³ hydrochloric acid has been investigated using a new approach of Mylius thermometric method. It is found that at low concentrations, the *o*-OH and *p*-OH compounds have the highest inhibition effect. Within the concentration range (5–10) × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³, the order is *p*-OCH₃ > *o*-OH > *p*-OH > *p*-N(CH₃)₂. A correlation with electronic structure, substituent and its position, concentration, nature and stability of the formed complexes and the inhibition order of the compounds has been discussed.

THE effect of additives on the rate of corrosion of aluminium and its alloys in hydrochloric acid has been the subject of many investigations, and the methods of comparing the efficiency of inhibition are numerous¹⁻⁴. Mylius⁵ developed a thermometric method for testing the corrosion of aluminium and its alloys. The variation of the temperature of the system is followed as a function of time and the reaction number (R.N.) is defined as $R.N. = (T_m - T_i)/t$ °C min⁻¹, where T_m and T_i are the maximum and initial temperatures respectively and t is the time (min) from the start of the experiment till the attainment of the maximum temperature.

Aziz and Shams El-Din⁶ studied the dissolution reaction of aluminium and zinc in hydrochloric acid using thermometric technique. The effect of a large number of additives such as urea, thiourea, gelatine, glycogen, starch and 8-hydroxyquinoline on the reaction number of aluminium in 2*N* HCl has been examined.

In this communication the effect of some 2-arylhydrazonobenzothiazoles on the rate of dissolution of Al—Mn alloy in 2.5 mol dm⁻³ hydrochloric acid was examined using the new approach of Mylius.

Experimental

The reaction vessel used was basically the same as described by Mylius⁵. Al—Mn alloy (2% Mn) test pieces (1 × 5 cm) were degreased⁶ with an alkaline mixture of Na₃PO₄ and Na₂CO₃ each of concentration 15 g dm⁻³ for 30 s at 80°. Each experiment was carried out with a fresh test piece and solution. The initial temperature in all the experiments was adjusted at 25°. All the corrosion tests were made in duplicate and the mean value was used. For each run, the required volume of the additive was transferred to a 25 ml measuring

flask containing hydrochloric acid and the mixture completed with double-distilled water.

The compounds 2-(*o*-OH, *p*-OH, *p*-OCH₃ and *p*-N(CH₃)₂ benzaldehyde)hydrazonobenzothiazoles were prepared as described in literature⁷, the m.p. being 250, 250, 190 and 240° respectively. Their C, H and N analyses were found satisfactory and their electronic and infrared spectral data agreed with the suggested structures⁸.

Results and Discussion

By following the temperature changes of the system in the absence and presence of different concentrations (1–10) × 10⁻⁴ mol dm⁻³ of the 2-arylhydrazonobenzothiazole compounds, the temperature of the system was found to change slightly during the initial stages of the reaction. After a certain period of time which depended upon the concentrations of the additives, the temperature rose to attain a maximum value. Representative temperature-time plots in presence of different concentrations of *p*-OCH₃ compound are given in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Effect of *p*-OCH₃ concentration on temperature-time curves of Al—Mn alloy in 2.5 mol dm⁻³ HCl.

TABLE 1—EFFICIENCY OF CORROSION INHIBITION AS DETERMINED BY REACTION NUMBER (R.N.)

Conc. $\times 10^{-4}$ mol dm ⁻³	<i>o</i> -OH		<i>p</i> -OH		<i>p</i> -OCH ₃		<i>p</i> -N(CH ₃) ₂	
	R.N.	I%	R.N.	I%	R.N.	I%	R.N.	I%
—	2.89	—	2.89	—	2.89	—	2.89	—
1	1.15	60.21	1.18	59.17	1.19	58.82	1.08	62.63
3	0.63	78.20	0.57	80.28	0.82	71.63	0.87	69.90
5	0.40	84.08	0.45	84.43	0.33	88.58	0.84	70.93
7	0.27	90.66	0.43	85.12	0.21	92.73	0.77	72.66
10	0.16	94.46	0.32	88.93	0.11	96.19	0.36	87.54

The data (Table 1) reveal that the efficiency of corrosion inhibition (*I*%) as determined from the percentage reduction in the reaction number (R.N.) varies both with the type and concentration of the compounds used. The inhibition-concentration (*I*% - *C*) curves for all the compounds are given in Fig. 2. It is obvious that at concentration upto 3×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³, the compounds can be arranged as *p*-OH \geq *o*-OH \geq *p*-OCH₃ $>$ *p*-N(CH₃)₂ in which *p* OH and *o*-OH have the highest inhibition effect. On the other hand, over 3×10^{-4} mol dm⁻³, the order is *p*-OCH₃ $>$ *o*-OH $>$ *p*-OH $>$ *p*-N(CH₃)₂. The comparison reveals that the order of the compound *p*-N(CH₃)₂ is unchanged. This behaviour may be explained by the fact that the efficiency is largely dependent on the area of the metal surface covered by one g-mole of the adsorbed molecule.

Fig. 2. Inhibition-concentration curves for all compounds used in presence of 2.5 mol dm⁻³ HCl.

In the present work, the compounds used have relatively high molecular weights (270–300) and the reaction number varies with both low and high concentrations indicating the formation of a primary and secondary adsorption layers. The variation in the reaction number is a function of the amount adsorbed and the latter is related to the bulk concentration through the adsorption coefficient. The conclusion is that the surface concentration also varies with the bulk concentration of the additive.

The application of reaction number calculations to estimate the inhibition efficiency (*I*%) as suggested by Mylius⁶ is more or less of qualitative nature as it does not consider the variation in temperature

and concentration during the corrosion process. Thus, the variation of temperature with time (*dT/dt*) was applied for calculation the inhibition efficiency⁹⁻¹¹.

The relation between log ΔT vs *t* was found to be a straight line obeying the empirical formula, $t = a + b \log \Delta T$, where *a* and *b* are constants; $a = t$ at $\Delta T = 1$ and *b* is the slope of the straight lines. Fig. 3 shows the log ΔT -*t* plot for *p*-OCH₃ compound as a representative data, other compounds

Fig. 3. Effect of *p*-OCH₃ concentration on log ΔT -*t* curves of Al-Mn alloy in 2.5 mol dm⁻³ HCl.

exhibiting the same behaviour. The values of the constants *a* (function of the corrosion rate in the stage of depassivation), *b* (function of the corrosion rate at $\Delta T > 1$) in absence of additives and *a'*, *b'* in their presence were obtained from that plot. The inhibition efficiencies (*I*%) values (Table 2) were calculated applying the relations, $I_{\Delta T=0.5^\circ} = (1 - a'/a) \times 100$ and $I_{\Delta T>0.5^\circ} = (1 - b'/b) \times 100$. Some of the data are presented graphically in Fig. 4 for the compounds *p*-OCH₃ and *p*-N(CH₃)₂ at $\Delta T = 0.5^\circ, \leq 2.5^\circ$ and $\leq 5.0^\circ$. The results indicate that the value of inhibition (*I*%) at the three chosen temperatures increases as the additive concentration increases. However, the values of *I*% at $\Delta T = 0.5^\circ$ are higher than that at $\Delta T \leq 2.5^\circ$, and that at $\Delta T \leq 2.5^\circ$ being better than that at $\Delta T \leq 5.0^\circ$. As

TABLE 2—INHIBITION COEFFICIENT ($I\%$) FOR THE COMPOUNDS IN 2.5 mol dm^{-3} HCl AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Concn. $\times 10^{-4}$ mol dm^{-3}	<i>o</i> -OH			<i>p</i> -OH			<i>p</i> -OCH ₃			<i>p</i> -N(CH ₃) ₂		
	$\Delta T: 0.5^\circ$	2.5	5.0	$\Delta T: 0.5^\circ$	2.5	5.0	$\Delta T: 0.5^\circ$	2.5	5.0	$\Delta T: 0.5^\circ$	2.5	5.0
1	66.67	76.00	75.00	63.64	45.47	30.01	57.90	50.00	41.70	69.23	62.49	53.36
3	75.00	66.67	66.67	69.23	72.72	68.19	82.22	69.99	65.01	71.93	62.49	56.26
5	81.82	70.01	70.06	83.33	70.01	65.03	92.86	62.49	50.04	74.60	60.00	50.04
7	82.61	82.35	80.00	85.19	66.67	61.13	95.12	81.25	78.14	76.47	60.00	50.04
10	88.73	76.93	76.47	86.09	66.67	61.13	96.19	80.00	75.01	85.46	72.72	68.19

 Fig. 4. Inhibition-concentration plots for *p*-OCH₃ and *p*-N(CH₃)₂ in presence of 2.5 mol dm^{-3} HCl at different temperatures.

the corrosion process progresses, the alloy surface is activated and the temperature starts to rise. So, the observed low values of $I\%$ at $\Delta T \leq 5.0^\circ$ relative to those at $\Delta T = 0.5^\circ$ and $\leq 2.5^\circ$ may be attributed to the lower adsorbability of these compounds on the activated surfaces than on the passive one.

All the compounds have N and S as key atoms for the process of adsorption in addition to the delocalised π -electrons of the two benzene rings through which the adsorption takes place. The presence of the OH group in *ortho*-position should increase the rate of charge transfer through the whole compound. Consequently, a high decrease in the corrosion rate should be expected in relation to the other compounds. However, within low concentration range upto $3 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, the order of *o*-OH was found parallel to that of *p*-OH. The coplanarity of benzene ring is more affected with *ortho*- than *para*-substituent resulting in a decrease in the rate of conjugation. Moreover, the expected hydrogen bond between the hydrogen of *o*-OH group and the nitrogen of the azomethine group may result a decrease in the polarity of the *o*-OH group and subsequently in the adsorption process. The order of *p*-OCH₃ compound after *o*-OH and *p*-OH is obviously due to concentration and stability factors. It seems that at the concentration range $(1-3) \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, the stoichiometry of 1:1 (metal: *p*-OCH₃) is not valid and consequently the product is unstable. The low inhibition detected for *p*-N(CH₃)₂ at both

low and high concentrations relative to the other compounds may be explained on the basis that the substituent *p*-N(CH₃)₂ is not planar and to the possible protonation of nitrogen in acidic medium, thus leading to distortion in the geometry of the structure and blocking the electrons.

On increasing the concentration within the range $(5-10) \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, the order was found to be *p*-OCH₃ > *o*-OH > *p*-OH > *p*-N(CH₃)₂. This is quite clear for electronic, concentration and stability factors. The donor character of *p*-OCH₃ group increases the rate of electron-transfer through the aromatic ring which facilitates the attraction with the positively charged metal surface. The increase in concentration of the additives increases the possibility of formation of stable products with both 1:1 and 1:2 (metal: additive) stoichiometry. The observed high inhibition values with *p*-OCH₃ could be due to the formation of 1:2 products with high stability in relation to the other compounds.

According to Basolo and Pearson¹⁵, Al³⁺ as Lewis acid has tightly held outer electrons and also an empty orbital. Basic atoms as oxygen, sulphur and nitrogen could coordinate by donating electrons to the empty orbitals of Al³⁺ forming a complex with different stabilities in acidic medium. Therefore, similar to other published work¹⁵⁻¹⁶, it can be concluded that the compounds under investigation have a strong tendency to form a stable complexes with Al³⁺ ions with ratio 1:1 and/or 1:2. The suggested structures can be represented as

where, R = *o*-OH, *p*-OH, *p*-OCH₃, *p*-N(CH₃)₂. From the coordination viewpoint¹⁷, the *o*-OH compound should show a high stable complex with ratio 1:1 and/or 1:2 within the concentration range used. This is based on the possibility of sharing the ionised *o*-OH groups in bonding with the Al³⁺ ions through (ONN) monobasic bidentate bonds.

The failure of this view in perhaps due to the difficult ionisation of the *o*-OH groups in acidic medium, the formation of intramolecular hydrogen bond with azomethine nitrogen group and finally to the distortion in the overall conjugation process.

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